

Part of

Investigating the role of small RNAs and their targets in mycorrhiza-mediated plant-to-plant signals towards improved pathogen tolerance

Description

AQUASERV | Molecular Biology & Omics | sequencing

Description

small RNA sequencing data reads

Researchers

Funder

CFLA

Grant

ANM_45_PG

Description

1 Summary

1.1 dataset type

1.1.1 Please specify the dataset type

plant small RNA reads

2 Your research data

2.1 Sequencing machine details

2.1.1 Sequencing chemistry / kits used

Illumina HighSeq500

2.2 General type of data

2.2.1 additional information about your dataset

small RNA reads

2.3 Type of data (format)

2.3.1 Data format

fastq or bam

2.4 Documentation and data quality

2.4.1 How will the data be documented and described/analysed? Please specify which type of documentation record are you planning to use (e.g. paper or electronic labbook, online resource) and which software are you planning to analyse your data with

electronic labbook

2.5 Storage and Backup

2.5.1 Do you use any intermediate storage devices? Please describe your backup plan.

PC, cloud and harddrive

2.6 Accessibility and long-term storage

2.6.1 Long term data storage - database

Genebank

2.6.2 Accession number

pending

2.7 Your metadata

2.7.1 Metadata format

excel

2.7.2 How is your metadata connected to the research data

BioProject description

2.7.3 Metadata storage

BioProject

3 Licence/embargo

3.1 Licence

3.1.1 Under what license will you publish your research data?

CC BY

3.2 Embargo on data release

3.2.1 Embargo details

Delay data release until manuscript acceptance

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